

DIFFUSION BONDING SiC-Ti METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A titanium-silicon carbide metal-matrix composite has been joined successfully using both solid-state and transient-liquid-phase (TLP) diffusion bonding; for the latter, a copper interlayer was used. The nature of the bonding surfaces was found to be important in order to obtain grain growth across the joint in solid-state bonding. In TLP bonding, the copper interlayer could be removed entirely provided sufficient time at temperature was given to eliminate any intermetallic phases at the bond-line.

A thin-film diffusion model was applied successfully to predict bonding times and temperatures for the TLP bonding. In order to optimise the bonding thermal cycle, the value of the activation energy for the diffusion of copper in the titanium matrix compared with that for the matrix-reinforcement reaction is of particular relevance. Their relative values were used in the model to account for the successful experimental approach of using relatively high temperatures for short times rather than lower temperatures for long times to obtain good bonds.

KEYWORDS: Composites; joint, diffusion bonded; solid-state and transient liquid phase; predictions of bonding conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal-matrix composites are being extensively studied, for instance as potential advanced aerospace materials, and titanium alloys reinforced with silicon carbide are of interest for such applications. As the SiC - Ti system is non-equilibrium, brittle intermetallic phases can readily form at the interfaces between the SiC reinforcement

and the Ti matrix. In order to minimise the formation of these brittle interfacial phases, coatings on the SiC reinforcement have been used successfully, e.g. carbon coating by chemical vapour deposition (1), and some fibre-type composites now are in industrial use. As industrial usage increases, joining of composites inevitably will be required in order to produce components of more complex designs.

Unless joining is achieved by adhesive bonding, the composites will be subjected to a thermal cycle during the joining process. Depending on the severity of the thermal cycle, there may be difficulties in retaining the original microstructure (e.g. the distribution of the reinforcement) as well as in minimising the extent of any reactions between matrix and reinforcement, and any such changes could adversely affect mechanical properties and perhaps lead to preferential corrosion in the bond region. Thus conventional fusion welding methods such as arc or resistance welding are likely to be of only limited use for joining composites since they cause extensive melting at the bond-line, with attendant problems of weld pool chemistry, as well as unacceptable disruption of, and interfacial reactions between, the reinforcement and matrix. In contrast, solid-state joining processes show more potential as far lower temperatures are required; for instance, diffusion bonding requires temperatures similar to those used when fabricating the composite. Accordingly, this paper summarises the results of an initial investigation into the diffusion bonding of an SiC - Ti composite. The work is part of a more general investigation into the joining of metal-matrix composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

In the present work, 12 mm diameter composite rods were used with particulate silicon carbide as reinforcement in a pure titanium matrix; the mean diameter of the SiC particles was 30 μm and the volume fraction was 10%.* Pure titanium (IMI 125) rod of 18 mm diameter was also used in order to provide a comparison to the composite material; the titanium was annealed at 675°C prior to use.

Bonding surfaces were ground to a 1200 grit finish on SiC paper and then ultrasonically cleaned in acetone. Samples were bonded for different times and temperatures using a radio-frequency induction furnace; the applied load was measured using a proof ring. Both temperature and pressure were continuously monitored and controlled by computer. A vacuum of better than 1×10^{-4} mbar was maintained during bonding.

* The fabrication of this material was carried out as follows. Both pure titanium powder and SiC particles were mixed by blender, sealed into a copper pipe, kept at 900°C for two hours, and finally extruded to 75% area reduction. The die of the extrusion machine was preheated to 300°C. Finally, the external copper pipe was removed by machining.

After joining, polished cross-sections of bonds were examined using light and scanning electron microscopies, and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) X-ray analysis also was carried out.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Solid state bonding A comparison of bond-line microstructures for both pure titanium and the composite material is shown in Figure 1. In pure titanium, grain growth occurs across the bond line and no bond line can be seen. In contrast, when bonding the composite, grain growth across the interface does not occur and the bond-line remains clearly visible. The difference in bonding behaviour was attributed to a thin film of silicide at the interface which formed from the SiC by reaction with the Ti matrix. EDS analysis showed the bond surfaces to be silicon rich; during the surface preparation, the relatively ductile titanium matrix both picks up SiC from the grinding paper as well as pieces of SiC from the composite itself. It was possible to eliminate the formation of the silicide film using a chemical etch (10% HF, 60% H₂O₂, balance H₂O) prior to bonding and the resulting bonds showed grain growth across the interface, similar to those in pure titanium.

A comparison of the extent of bonding for pure titanium compared with that for the composite is shown in Figure 2a for the initial stages of bonding at two different temperatures. Although interface diffusion might be expected to be greater in the composite due to the large number of reinforcement-matrix interfaces, the overall rate of bonding is slower for the composite. This is attributed to the larger initial void size formed when bonding the composite. In the initial stages of bonding, it is evident that the voids near the SiC reinforcement are larger than those where there is no reinforcement - see Figure 3. It is assumed that the reinforcement is hard enough to deform the Ti matrix but that the matrix does not plastically flow sufficiently to instantaneously fill in the voids under the bonding conditions used. This interpretation is supported by modelling the bonding process using the model of Hill and Wallach (2). The data used in the model for peak-to-valley roughness and wavelength were approximately 3 μm and 10 μm for the pure titanium samples, and 10 μm and 30 μm respectively for the composite. The predicted results of bonding under the same conditions as those used experimentally are shown in Figure 2b and, for the pure titanium, show good agreement with the measured values.

The growth of reaction layers between the SiC reinforcement and the Ti matrix has been studied by Marteneau et al (3). The thickness of the reaction layer, x , was shown to increase linearly with the square root of the heating time, t , at a given temperature providing the reaction layer was not too thick, i.e.

$$x = k t^{0.5} \quad (1)$$

The material constant, k , follows an Arrhenius temperature dependence and so equation (1) becomes

$$x = k_0 \exp(-Q_r / 2RT) t^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

where R is the gas constant, k_0 is a constant, T is the absolute temperature and Q_r is the activation energy for the diffusion phenomenon. In the temperature range 700 to 1100°C, the measured values of Q_r and k_0 were 227 kJ mol⁻¹ and 0.37 cm s^{-0.5} respectively.

Marteneau et al (3) reported that the reaction layers found between silicon carbide and titanium alloys were binary mixtures of non-stoichiometric titanium carbide and titanium silicide. In the present work, two regions were observed at the reaction layer. TiC was found nearer the original SiC reinforcement and a mixture of TiC and Ti₅Si₃ was adjacent to the Ti matrix. The growth of these phases has been examined in more detail and is reported elsewhere (4).

In summary, it is possible to estimate the optimum bonding conditions using the solid-state model of diffusion bonding of Hill and Wallach (2). In addition, the extent of the reaction layer between the SiC reinforcement and Ti matrix likely to form using the optimum bonding conditions can be predicted using the data of Marteneau et al (3).

3.2 Transient liquid phase (TLP) bonding The basis of transient liquid phase bonding is well documented elsewhere (5). Typical results from the current study, using a 5 µm copper foil at a temperature of 900°C, are shown in Figure 4. In the initial stages of bonding, three layers can be seen at the bond line; an eutectic layer in the centre, intermetallic compounds in the middle and a martensitic outer layer*. As bonding proceeds, the eutectic and intermetallic layers are eliminated by further interdiffusion and it is reasonable to assume that satisfactory bond-line strengths will be attained only when these layers have disappeared. Accordingly, a model is required in order to predict the formation and elimination of the various bond-line phases.

3.3 Modelling transient liquid phase bonding. The compositions of the bond-line phases during the TLP bonding process can be predicted from the Cu-Ti equilibrium diagram, and their growth can be modelled using a thin-film diffusion solution (6), namely:

$$C_{(x,t)} = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{\pi D_B t}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{4D_B T}\right) \quad (3)$$

* Both the intermetallic and martensitic layers are not as simple microstructurally as implied above. A fuller description is given elsewhere (4).

where $C_{(x,t)}$ = concentration of solute (%)
 M = initial quantity of solute in interlayer (cm %)
 x = distance from original bond-line (cm)
 t = time (s)
 D_B = diffusion coefficient for interlayer ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$).

Using this equation, smooth composition profiles of the interlayer material (in this case, copper) across the bond-line can be calculated for different bonding times and temperatures. In a simplified approach, each layer at the bond-line can be assumed to have a composition range (in weight % copper) as follows:

eutectic layer	intermetallic layer	martensitic layer
100 - 75	75 - 12	12 - 2

Using the above assumed values, the widths of each of the three layers are calculated (see Figure 5), and then each width is multiplied by a density factor (determined by dividing the density of copper by the density of the phase) in order to allow for the effects of differences in density of each phase. The results of this simple approach are shown in Figure 6 in which the widths of the different phases are plotted as a function of time using a particular bonding temperature. It is evident that there is good agreement between the experimental results and the calculated predictions. Hence this approach allows the prediction of suitable bonding conditions for TLP bonding if it is assumed that a satisfactory bond strength is attained when the copper-rich intermetallic layer disappears.

3.4 Reaction layer growth versus optimal TLP bonding time. It is clear that TLP bonding has the potential to join SiC-Ti composites. However, as has been discussed earlier, the extent of the reaction between matrix and reinforcement also is an important factor when joining composites and also needs to be minimised.

Using the above assumption, that optimum bonding properties will be obtained when the intermetallic phase has just disappeared from the bond-line, the optimum time for bonding t_B can be estimated from equation (3) above. When the intermetallic phase first disappears, the copper concentration at the centre of the bond-line (i.e. at $x=0$) must have decreased to the maximum concentration of copper in the martensitic layer, assumed above to be 12% and denoted here as C_M . Rearranging equation (3) and letting $x=0$ gives:

$$\sqrt{t_B} = \frac{M}{C_M 2\sqrt{\pi D_B}} \quad (4)$$

Using an Arrhenius dependence for D_B , equation (4) becomes:

$$\sqrt{t_B} = \frac{M}{C_M 2\sqrt{\pi D_0} \exp(-Q_B/RT)} \quad (5)$$

Not surprisingly, the above equation shows that the time required for bonding decreases as the bonding temperature increases.

In order to estimate the extent of interfacial reaction between the SiC reinforcement and the Ti matrix for the optimal bonding conditions as defined by equation (5), the value of t_B defined in equation (5) can be substituted in equation (2)

$$x = \frac{k_0 M}{2C_M \sqrt{\pi D_0}} \exp(Q_B - Q_r / 2RT) \quad (6)$$

From this equation, it can be seen that the extent and temperature dependence of intermetallic growth around the reinforcement depends, in part, on the relative values of the two activation energies Q_r and Q_B . With regard to temperature dependence, the width of the reaction layer increases as the bonding temperature rises when Q_r is bigger than Q_B , while the reverse occurs when Q_r is smaller than Q_B and the width decreases if higher bonding temperatures (albeit for shorter times) are used to effect TLP bonding.

This result can be shown more clearly as follows. For the diffusion of copper in titanium, values of $Q_B = 331 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $D_0 = 3.16 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ have been reported by Wells (7) although other values are also reported (8). The values obtained by Marteneau et al (3) for Q_r and D_0 for the growth of the reaction layers between the SiC reinforcement and the Ti matrix have been given above. Using these values, the results shown in Figure 7 are obtained and it is clear that the fall in the optimal bonding time as temperature increases is much greater than the increase in width of the interfacial layer.

Using the above approach, it is also possible to calculate times at different temperatures required to grow the same thickness of the reaction layer; typical results are as follows:

3600 s at 900°C

270 s at 1000°C

30 s at 1100°C.

The bond-line microstructures for these joining conditions are shown in Figure 8. There is not a large difference between the various conditions although, as predicted

by the above calculations, the width of martensitic layer becomes smaller as temperature rises.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The work reported in this paper suggests that both solid-state bonding and TLP bonding are promising methods for joining titanium composites. Modelling these joining processes is useful not only to minimise trial and error experiments but also to minimise the effects of the thermal cycles necessary when bonding. For TLP bonding, the results from a thin-film diffusion model give good agreement with experimental data and optimum bonding condition may be predicted. It was found that when joining the SiC-Ti composite, the use of high temperatures and short times appears more beneficial than the use of low temperatures for longer time in minimising the interfacial reaction between the SiC reinforcement and Ti matrix.

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Figure 1. Solid-state diffusion bonds [bonding conditions of 850°C, 5 MPa, 60 min.].

Figure 2. Extent of bonded area as a function of bonding time [pressure 5 MPa].

a. Adjacent to SiC reinforcement 5 μm b. Away from SiC reinforcement

Figure 3. Initial bond line voids [bonding conditions of 800°C, 5 MPa, 10 min.].

Figure 4. Sequence of TLP bonds in pure titanium using 10 μm thick Cu foil at 900°C.

Figure 5. Representation of the model for the calculation of layer widths in TLP bonding.

a. Experimental results

b. Theoretical predictions

Figure 6. Bond-line layer widths in TLP bonds using 10 μm thick copper foils at 900°C.

Figure 7. Calculated reaction layer widths from interdiffusion between SiC and Ti. The times used are those calculated for the optimum TLP bonding condition assuming a final copper concentration at the bond-line of either 5 or 12 %.

a. 3600 s at 900°C.

b. 270 s at 1000°C.

c. 30 s at 1100°C

100 μm

Figure 8. TLP bond-line microstructures using equivalent thermal cycles.